

The Dissociation Constant of Eugenol.

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Lunden (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1910, 70, 249) has determined the dissociation constants of phenols by measuring the hydrolysis of their salts. He pointed out that very accurate results can be attained only if the salt of the phenol undergoes a large hydrolysis. Consequently he recommends the investigation of the ammonium salt instead of sodium or potassium salt. In the case of eugenol the same method can be applied; only eugenol being difficultly soluble in ammonia caustic soda had to be used.

Assuming that sodium eugenate and hydroxide dissociate completely and eugenol does not at all dissociate, which is only approximately true, we can write

$$X = \frac{K_v - K_s}{K_{OH} - K_a}$$

where X is the fraction of eugenate hydrolysed and K_v , K_s , and K_{OH} represent respectively the equivalent conductivity of the solution of sodium eugenate at the dilution of V litres, that of the salt solution with the hydrolysis suppressed and of sodium hydroxide solution. K_s is determined after suppressing the hydrolysis by the addition of an excess of eugenol. X , the degree of hydrolysis being found, the hydrolysis constant K_h is evaluated by the relation,

$$K_h = \frac{X^2}{(1-X)V}$$

V being the dilution. Then the dissociation constant K_a is related to the dissociation constant of water K_w by the relation,

$$K_a = \frac{K_w}{K_h}$$

EXPERIMENTAL.

A sample of eugenol was distilled after drying over anhydrous magnesium sulphate. The distillation was repeated until the distillate was almost colourless. This was considered pure since its refractive index was the same when purified by acetylation and subsequent hydrolysis with alkali.

The caustic soda employed was prepared from metallic sodium and during the preparation care was taken to exclude atmospheric carbon dioxide. It was diluted with gas-free, conductivity water and preserved free from atmospheric carbon dioxide. The solution was standardised by weight with pure oxalic acid.

The solutions of sodium eugenate were made in every experiment by mixing equivalent amounts of sodium hydroxide solution and freshly distilled eugenol. The hydrolysis in these solutions was suppressed when required by the addition of a few drops of eugenol.

The conductivity vessel employed had two platinum electrodes of 1 cm. diameter and about 2.5 cm. apart and was provided with a thermometer stopper.

While carrying out an experiment a definite weight of the standard alkali was treated with an exactly equivalent amount of eugenol. This solution was diluted to the required concentration by the addition of weighed quantity of freshly distilled water. A small amount of this solution was transferred into the cell and its conductivity determined. Excess of eugenol was shaken with the remaining solution for some time and the conductivity of that solution was also similarly determined.

It was found that eugenol does not readily dissolve in weak alkali and, therefore, always a strong solution of alkali was treated with eugenol and the solution was diluted afterwards. The low solubility of eugenol is an obstacle to the complete and quick suppression of hydrolysis, especially when the solution is dilute. Therefore higher dilutions than 50 litres were not tried.

In the following table the results of a series of experiments all conducted at 25° are given. V denotes the dilution in litres. K_0 and K_1 , the equivalent conductivity of hydrolysed and unhydrolysed salt solutions respectively; a , the percentage of hydrolysis; K_h , the

hydrolysis constant ; K_a , the dissociation constant of eugenol. For the water constant K_w , Kohlrausch's value 1.11×10^{-14} is taken.

Expt.	V.	K_v	K_s	α	$K_a \times 10^4$	$K_a \times 10^{10}$
1	9.49	63.51	57.18	3.4	1.24	0.89
2	13.69	67.61	61.45	3.4	0.86	1.30
3	13.69	67.42	61.90	3.0	0.69	1.62
4	14.80	67.11	60.49	3.6	0.91	1.23
5	14.92	66.65	59.05	4.2	1.24	0.90
6	17.37	70.20	63.46	3.7	0.83	1.34
7	17.46	70.11	63.37	3.7	0.82	1.35
8	24.82	73.30	65.19	4.6	0.86	1.29
9	24.87	73.05	65.33	4.3	0.78	1.43
10	24.97	73.37	65.19	4.8	0.96	1.13
11	25.00	73.10	65.06	4.5	0.84	1.32
12	46.34	79.34	67.69	6.6	1.00	1.11
13	46.58	79.09	67.44	6.6	0.99	1.12
14	47.06	79.75	67.84	6.8	1.03	1.97
15	47.58	80.83	68.74	6.9	1.36	1.04
16	47.60	80.15	68.34	6.9	1.01	1.10
17	47.84	80.46	68.92	6.6	0.97	1.15

CONCLUSION.

In the above solutions it is only an approximation to assume complete dissociation of the sodium eugenate as they are still not sufficiently dilute. The progressive increase in K_v with dilution shows that dissociation of the salt is not quite complete even at 50 litres dilution. This is responsible for the change in the value of K_a and K_s noticed with changing dilution.

The above values for K_a , however, can give us an idea of the strength of eugenol as an acid. The dissociation constant is of the order of 1×10^{-10} and therefore eugenol is about as acidic as phenol itself. Regarding the actual value of the dissociation constant, its determination is accurate only at very high dilutions.

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